

Relative volumes of representative regions involved in sensory and emotional processings
in LTI ● and STI ● quails

Group
F=35.716, p<0.0001
Hemisphere
F=17.085, p=0.0006
Interaction
F=9.115, p=0.007

Group
F=5.622, p=0.029
Hemisphere
F=99.775, p<0.0001
Interaction
F=1.8, p=0.196

Group
F=35.716, p<0.0001
Hemisphere
F=17.085, p=0.0006
Interaction
F=9.115, p=0.007

Group
F=0.596, p=0.45
Hemisphere
F=11.495, p=0.003
Interaction
F=0.022, p=0.885

Group
F=9.953, p=0.005
Hemisphere
F=111.734, p<0.0001
Interaction
F=0.097, p=0.759